

The Role Of The Faculty Members At The Hashemite University In Strengthening The Values Of Global Citizenship From The Students' Point Of View

Fawwaz Yasein Salman, Ibrahim Mohammad Harafsheh

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 03, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Values Of The Global Citizenship, The Hashemite University</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4494549</p>	<p><i>This study aimed at identifying the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University in strengthening the values of the global citizenship, as seen by the students of the University students. The study population comprised all the Hashemite University male and female students (n=21381). The sample consisted of (850) male and female who were chosen by the random, stratified method. To achieve the study objectives, the researcher constructed a questionnaire to identify the students' responses on the role of the faculty members in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship. The results showed that the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University, as viewed by its students, was medium. There were statistically significant differences in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship ascribed to the gender variable, which was in favor of the males. On the other hand, there were no statistically significant differences in the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University in reinforcing the global citizenship ascribed to the faculty variable.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The world recently witnessed successive, rapid changes and developments, which rendered the change process inevitable to accommodate these developments and contain their implications in most countries of the world. This further made our Islamic and Arab communities accept these changes but with caution for fear of affecting the values, principles, habits and traditions of these communities (Al-Kaltham, 2016).

In addition, the world is experiencing political conflicts, problems, and turmoil, economical exploitation, and the domination of the rich over the poor countries (Aljawarneh & Al-Omari, 2018). The adverse consequences that resulted from the colonial powers created the belief of the necessity to find a global formula for cooperation and understanding between the peoples and nations (Al-Omari et al., 2020). and that the cooperation and understanding are the optimal way to avoid all these cultural, economic and political struggles (Al-Da'abseh, et al., 2018). These global crises and problems can only be solved globally, which requires stimulating people to embrace the concept of the global citizenship, and bear the entailed responsibilities toward this planet, and care for the issues of those who live with them on it (Al-Ahmadi, 2012).

These rapid global changes and developments posed a great challenge to the higher education responsibilities, which mandates keeping a pace with these developments in a manner that preserves the culture and identity of the nation through its educational mission that is embodied in the teacher, who is the target of the faculties of education in the Jordanian universities to prepare, train and qualify him to upgrade his performance level.

From this standpoint, it is incumbent upon the student of faculties of education to be aware of all the life aspects, observe the human rights when dealing with his students after graduation. He is further required to enhance the intellectual and cultural diversity, spread the values of peace and democracy, and seek to find solutions of the environmental problems that the world is suffering from, through applying the true scientific bases to solve the problems the humanity is facing worldwide (Saleem, 2011).

The global citizenship advocates the idea of individual's preparation and interaction with his peers in a world dominated by multiculturalism and rapid change; as well as the effective human contribution in leading the world toward progress and scientific development of a global perspective based on achieving justice, equality, and international security and peace (Al-Taskhiri, 2001).

Makram (2004) provides that the most important traits of citizenship are wide command of the domestic and international matters and issues, effective contribution to the community building, taking rational decisions to face the environmental problems, and possession of the required thinking skills to adapt and coexist with the age civilization. Accordingly, the global citizenship responsibilities extend far beyond the borders of the nation to face the global issues that obstacle the human progress (Aqel et al., 2020).

The global citizenship is the human's feeling that the world he lives in is for all, and that there is a human system that rules the world in spite of the political differences, the economic interests and the multiculturalism, because of the bad need for facilitated laws and dominating powers that influence the world progress and

development (M. Sokiyna et al., 2020). This is indicative of the urgent need to a common understanding and collective sense among the world nations of all what they face of changes, both in the present or future times (Al-Mousa, 2005).

Rooting of the global citizenship is among the value considerations in the formation of the university youth as assets added to the community body, rather than opponents cut off the entity of this body (Alshare et al., 2020). Therefore, education of the university students for the sake of the global citizenship is one of the most controversial and loud issues in the field of the contemporary education (Aljawarneh et al., 2020). This requires reconsidering certain basic standpoints of education in all whatever related to the global citizenship in the university students' behavior, their status in the social texture, and their aspired role in solving many of the global problems that all of us suffer from (Al-Udwan and Bani Mustafa, 2015).

Values of the global citizenship are the most important issues that should receive focus and rooting in the selves and behaviors of the university students (Aljawarneh & Atan, 2018). as it is an added strength to the state and symbol of its civilization (Alsafadi et al., 2020). It is the safety valve of the nation and its interests, in which the nations can progress and grow, and people possess the will of coexistence and ability to achieve it (Munsif Sokiyna & Aqel, 2020). It is not acceptable that the issue of values is dealt with as a matter that we take care of from time to time (Alomari et al., 2020). as per the situations and conditions, only when the problem comes to the surface or erupts (Mahafzah et al., 2020). Since the researcher is deeply and continuously concerned, as an academic, in the development of the global citizenship with his students, he noticed a clear shortcoming of the students' knowledge and understanding about the global citizenship, as well as their interest in the human common issues in the Kingdom. As a result, this study was conducted to diagnose the reality scientifically, through learning the role of the faculty members in the Hashemite University in strengthening the values of the global citizenship from the view of its students, by answering the following two questions.

- 1- What is the role of the Hashemite University faculty members in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship as viewed by the students?
- 2- Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) level in the study sample evaluations of the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship according to the gender and faculty variables?

Objectives

The research aims at

- Identifying the role of the faculty members in supporting the values of the global citizenship in the Hashemite University through the responses of the students to the study axes.
- Detecting the differences in the study sample evaluations of the role of the faculty members in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship in the Hashemite University attributed to the gender and faculty variables.

Significance of the Study

The study significance stems from:

- Introducing the faculty members to their role in supporting the global citizenship, developing this role to fit the global citizenship culture, and instilling the associated authentic values among the university students.
- The anticipated importance of the results of the study which may be an aid to the university and higher education officials for setting curricula and suitable knowledge, to find the good citizen, who belongs to the homeland and is committed to the principles of the good citizenship.
- The researcher hopes that the study will attract the attention of the researchers to conduct many studies in the topic of global citizenship values, and the mechanism to support it among the university students.

Procedural Definitions

Values: a pool of desired social rules and standards the university student acquires. They will develop his personality, direct his behavior, organize his life, and guarantee his positive interaction with others. These standards will form a referential standard that controls his behaviors, tendencies, desires and interests, and will lead him to perform his role effectively in the environment where he is.

Global citizenship: a number of standards and principles that should be taken into account when preparing the students in the university. These principles comprise: the global peace, democracy, human rights, the human and environment, and the scientific thinking. It is procedurally measured by the degree the sample participants obtain in their responses the items of the questionnaire.

Study Limits:

The thematic limits: the study was limited to indentifying the role of the faculty members in the Hashemite University in strengthening the values of the global citizenship.

The geographical limits: the study was conducted in the Hashemite University only.

The human limits: the study was limited to a sample of the Hashemite University students.

The time limits: the researcher conducted the field study during the second semester (2018/2019).

Previous studies:

The researcher reviewed the following studies:

- Al-Sagheer (2012) conducted an analytical study that aimed at identifying the concept of education for the global citizenship and its significance, as well as the importance of taking into account and showing certain universal trends of this education. The study concluded by developing a proposed perception of the Egyptian school role in the pre-university education in educating the global citizen in the light of the global trends and the nature of the Egyptian community. The study also included recommendations such as: the need to include the global dimension to the education system inside the school; organizing programs that target the cultural exchange with other countries; supporting the educational programs that develop the global role and achieve the national security; and benefiting from the experiences of other countries in integrating the global education concepts in certain courses that are taught to the students inside the school.
- Abu Salamiah (2009) conducted a study in Palestine that aimed to identify the performance degree of the education colleges of their role in supporting the citizenship of its students according to the academic level, gender and the educational institution. The sample included (487) male and female students in the Palestinian universities in Gaza, and the study instrument was the questionnaire. The study concluded that the education colleges support the citizenship at a medium level, with statistically significant differences in favor of the males.
- Harney (2007) made a study to identify the effect of the university in teaching the students the rights and duties of citizenship and their role in the community. The study provided important results such as: the students' practice of the different activities inside the university; their participation in the dialogues and discussions with the teachers and the issues of the community issues and problems; understanding the social and political issues inside and outside the university; preparing them to deal with the challenges that face in life; and teaching them the democratic method, contributed in implanting and supporting the citizenship values with them.
- Al-Khiyari (2007) conducted a study titled "The theoretical foundation for acquiring the global citizenship", aimed at identifying the theoretical constituents that help the Moroccan high school students acquire the values of the global citizenship values, as viewed by a sample of the high school teachers. The study adopted the descriptive analytical method, and made a number of conclusions. The most important were: emphasis on the re-establishment of the educational relationship inside the Moroccan high school according to the principles of democracy, dialogue and partnership with the other, and enablement of the teachers of the best pedagogic ways to form the values of the global citizenship among the students, particularly those associated to the human rights, tolerance and dialogue with the other.
- McDougall's study (2005) emphasized that the global citizenship concept is actually embodied through the involvement of the individual, either at the local or global level. In his analyses of the students' experiences, he found that education of the global citizenship may lead to the individual's development and the mutual cultural understanding.
- Al-Kareem (2003) investigated the role of the youth care in the Egyptian universities in the development of citizenship with their students. It aimed at identifying the citizenship concept and dimensions and the important contemporary changes and their effect on the citizenship; as well as identifying the youth care activities and their role in developing the citizenship. The study concluded with a proposed perception through which this role can be activated in the Egyptian universities for the development of citizenship with the students. The researcher recommended the necessity of activating the youth care role in the universities in strengthening the citizenship values with the university youth.
- Karsten (2003) conducted a study in Mexico that aimed at identifying the effects of the university international activities and programs in Mexico on activating the citizenship values with the students. The study was applied in both Mexico and Canada and concluded that the teaching method and research that is based on community participation and ongoing training on dealing and interaction with the community problems in their learning inside the university, helped in supporting the citizenship values among the students. Furthermore, there was an awareness of the students and involvement in the changes and transformations that take place in the community.

The above previous studies show the diversified environments where the ability to support the citizenship values was taught. We also notice that these studies tackled different issues, such as the global citizenship values and the citizenship values inside the state. All these studies indicated the existence of a positive connotation in strengthening the citizenship values by the universities or colleges

The researcher benefited from these studies in developing the objectives of the current study, questions, procedures, ways of data analyses, and supporting the discussion of its results concerning agreement or disagreement with these studies. However, this study attempted to identify the role of the faculty members in the Hashemite University in strengthening the values of the global citizenship as viewed by the students, as well as in another community and within other variables. In addition, this study is one of the few studies in the Hashemite University that tackled this issue, as far the researcher's best knowledge goes.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive method that is based on describing the phenomenon by collecting its data, classifying and analyzing them, and linking among their implications, to reach an understanding of the studied phenomenon and the variables that affect them using the questionnaire. The researcher determined the sample and the instrument and its applications, as well as the suitable statistical analyses for the study objectives and questions.

Study Population

The study population comprised all the male and female university students (n=21831) during the second semester of the academic year 2018/2019.

Study Sample

The sample consisted of (850) male and female students who were chosen from the study population by the random stratified method, and Table (1) shows the distribution of the sample according to the personal variables.

Table (1): Distribution of the Sample According o the Study Variables

Variable	Level	No.	Percentage
Gender	Male	440	52
	Female	410	48
	Total	850	100
College	Education	293	34
	Arts	287	34
	Science	270	32
	Total	850	100

Study Instrument

The instrument consisted of two parts; the first part included general information of the respondent, i.e. gender and college. The second is the major part of the questionnaire that measures the role of the faculty members in the Hashemite University in strengthening the values of the global citizenship as viewed by its students. The researcher constructed it by reviewing the educational literature that is related to values. The questionnaire, in its initial shape, consisted of (44) items distributed over four domains (global peace, democracy, human rights, and educational environment). The items were formulated as per Likert five-point scale, which range was (Very high, high, medium, low, and very low degrees). The highest score was given five grades and the lowest one grade. The grades are arranged in a descending order: 5, 4, 3, 2, 1.

The following scale was adopted for the result analyses:

1-1.8	very low
1.81-2.6	low
2.61-3.4	medium
3.41-4.2	high
4.21-5	very high

If the items were negative, then they will be reversed during entering in the statistical analysis program.

Study Instrument Validity

The researcher verified the apparent performance of the instrument validity by introducing it to a group of arbitrators of the Jordanian universities faculty members to benefit from their views and guidance about the suitability degree of the items to the study domains, checking the clarity degree of the items and the language integrity, as well as implementing any other addition or deletion of any phrase or item as per their comments. Thereafter, the researcher chose the items which had the approval of half or more of the arbitrators, taking into consideration all their comments whether on the language phrasing, clarity of the items, connection degree of the item with the domain it belongs to, addition, deletion or amendment. Then the instrument was adopted in its final shape with (39) items distributed as follows: (7) for the global peace domain, (11) for democracy, (13) for the human rights, and (8) for the environmental education domain.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was verified by test-retest procedures. It was applied to a sample of (25) male and female students, with two weeks' interval between the first and second tests. The reliability

coefficient was calculated using Pearson coefficient, which showed that the correlation coefficient of the instrument, as a whole, was (0.87) that indicates the validity of the instrument for the study purposes.

Study Variables

The study included three variables; two independent and one dependent. The independent variables are the (gender and college), and the dependent variable is the role of the Hashemite University faculty members in supporting the values of the global citizenship as seen by its students.

Results Analysis and discussion:

Results of the first question: What is the role of the Hashemite University faculty members in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship as viewed by the students?

To answer this question, the researcher obtained the means (Ms) and standard deviations (SDs) of the domains of the global citizenship as per the students' views, and of the instrument as a whole, as illustrated in Table (2).

Table (2) Means and Standard Deviations of the Domains of the Global Citizenship Values as Viewed by the Students, and for the Instrument as a Whole.

No.	Domain	M	SD	Level of Support	Order
1	Global Peace	2.71	0.70	Medium	2
2	Democracy	2.87	0.79	Medium	1
3	Human rights	2.66	0.76	Medium	3
4	Environmental education	2.64	0.83	medium	4
	The Instrument as a Whole	2.72	0.75	Medium	

Table (2) shows that the means of the study sample participants on its domains ranged between (2.87-2.64) and were at medium levels for all the domains. The highest was for democracy (M=2.87) and the lowest was for the environmental education (M=2.64).

In general, the instrument, as a whole, was at medium level (M=2.72). The researcher ascribes this to the existence of a type of support to the global citizenship by the faculty members. Yet, it did not match an actual guidance and direct, influential teaching method in fixing these values with the students, both in their behaviors and practices in their community. This result is in line with Abu Salamiah's study (2009), which showed that the faculties of education in the Palestinian universities support the citizenship at a medium level.

The means and standard deviations of the sample participants' responses on the items of every domain of the study instrument individually were extracted; Tables (3, 4, and 5) illustrate the particulars.

Table (3) Means and Standard Deviations of the Sample Participants' Responses on the Items of "Global Peace" Domain.

No.	Item	M	SD	Level of Support
1	Calls for the respect of life and termination of violence through education and dialogue.	3.48	0.53	High
2	Encourages eliminating all types of racism, racial discrimination, hatred of foreigners, and the related fanaticism.	3.31	0.61	medium
3	Enhances the understanding, tolerance and solidarity culture among the civilizations, peoples and cultures.	2.65	0.67	Medium
4	Encourages the students to take part in the initiatives during the conflict times, such as "medicine distribution, and foodstuffs."	2.63	0.69	Medium
5	Encourages the students to train on methods for conflict management and solution.	2.35	0.66	Low
6	Promotes the global peace culture by exchange of information with the students.	2.29	0.76	Low
7	Encourages developing active partnerships between the different parties to strengthen the peace concept.	2.25	0.72	Low
	The Domain as a Whole	2.71	0.70	Medium

Table (3) indicates that the means of the global peace items ranged between 3.48 (highest), which was for the item providing, "Calls for the respect of life and termination of violence through education and dialogue", and 2.25 (lowest), which was for the item providing, "Encourages developing active partnerships between the different parties to strengthen the peace concept". As for the domain as a whole, the level was medium with (2.71) mean and (0.70) standard deviation. This result may be ascribed to that the faculty members have a role in strengthening the global peace among the students. Even though, the level did not reach the

aspired degree by fixing the concepts of the global peace and making them a culture that the students deal in inside and outside the campus.

Table (4) Means and Standard Deviations of the Sample Participants' Responses on the Items of "Democracy" Domain, Arranged in a Descending Order.

No.	Item	M	SD	Level of Support
1	Encourages the freedoms and human rights.	3.27	0.53	Medium
2	Develops the ability to express the opinion	3.24	0.61	Medium
3	Urges not to judge exclusively and exclude the other.	3.17	0.67	Medium
4	Urges to accept the other and listen to the points of view.	3.16	0.69	Medium
5	Calls for the rejection of violence and use of force for solving the problems.	3.01	0.66	medium
6	Enhances the students' ability to influence in decision taking.	2.86	0.76	Medium
7	Encourages the harmony in dialogue and non-persistence in situations.	2.84	0.72	Medium
8	Encourages the necessity to get rid of the fanaticism aspects.	2.79	0.83	Medium
9	Enhances in the students that dialogue is the only way to solve the problems.	2.77	0.89	Medium
10	Explains to the students that the individual's dignity stems from his commitment to his duties and the rules of the country were he is found.	2.24	0.82	Low
11	Develops the ability to practice positive opposition.	2.22	0.82	Low
	The Domain as a Whole	2.87	0.79	medium

Table (4) shows that the means of the democracy domain items ranged between 3.27 (higher), which was for the item providing, "Encourages the freedoms and human rights ", and 2.22 (lowest), which was for the item providing, "Develops the ability to practice positive opposition". As for the domain as a whole, it was with (2.87) mean and (0.79) standard deviation. The researcher imputes this result to the ineffectiveness of the faculty members in supporting the democracy values with the students. In this concern, their focus may be only on the curriculum and not to link it with democracy, as a trend to concentrate on the educational courses and not to intervene with any thing other than this.

Table (5) Means and Standard Deviations of the Sample Participants' Responses on the Items of "Human Rights" Domain, Arranged in a Descending Order.

No.	Item	M	SD	Level of Support
1	Believes in the far going saying "My freedom stops at the borders of the others' freedom".	3.00	0.53	Medium
2	Calls the students to openness on the global cultures.	2.86	0.56	Medium
3	Urges the students to avoid any aggressive behavior.	2.83	0.61	Medium
4	Makes the students aware of the importance of difference and diversity in enhancing the human civilization.	2.76	0.67	Medium
5	Coordinates the participation of the students in introductory courses of the human rights and citizenship culture.	2.76	0.69	Medium
6	Guides students to their responsibilities in protecting the human rights from any infringement.	2.73	0.66	Medium
7	Calls the students for tolerance in the relations with others.	2.71	0.76	Medium
8	Calls the students for the effective participation in the voluntary work.	2.70	0.72	Medium
9	Applies fairness and equality among the students.	2.70	0.83	Medium
10	Calls the students to respect the human right in the social media.	2.54	0.89	Low
11	Develops awareness of the students on the importance of the right in living within a civilian community.	2.42	0.94	Low
12	Increases the students' awareness on the right to get the constituents of the social security.	2.29	0.99	Low
13	Guides the students to the right in an educational environment	2.25	0.91	Low

	characterized by quality standards.			
	The Domain as a Whole	2.66	0.76	Medium

Table (5) shows that the means of the human right domain items ranged between 3.00 (highest), which was for the item providing, "Believes in the far going saying "My freedom stops at the borders of the others' freedom", and 2.25 (lowest), which was for the item providing, " Guides the students to the right in an educational environment characterized by quality standards". The domain, as a whole, was at a medium level with (2.66) mean and (0.76) standard deviation. The researcher ascribes this to the existence of a type of evaluation, yet it did not reach the aspired level of guidance and support that encourages the student live within a civilian life far from the aggressive behavior, where the human's humanity.

Table (6) Means and Standard Deviations of the Sample Participants' Responses on the Items of "Environmental Education" Domain, Arranged in a Descending Order.

No.	Item	M	SD	Level of Support
1	Develops the ethical values with the students in a way that helps in activating the positive relation between the human and environment.	3.03	0.52	Medium
2	Helps the students to acquire awareness on the holistic environment through explaining the environmental concepts.	2.95	0.59	Medium
3	Highlights the ill effects of the misuse of the natural resources.	2.88	0.61	Medium
4	Urges the students to participate in preventive programs on the environmental pollution.	2.64	0.59	Medium
5	Encourages ideas, information and experiences related to the environmental education among the world countries.	2.48	0.67	Low
6	Encourages the students to carry out research that leads to a better understanding of the environmental education objectives.	2.41	0.69	Low
7	Encourages the students to hold exhibitions and participate in the different environmental committees inside the college.	2.39	0.66	Low
8	Develops a sense of the individual and collective responsibility in protecting the environment through the one-team work spirit and through participation in solving the environmental problems.	2.33	0.72	Low
	The Domain as a Whole	2.64	0.82	Medium

It is quite clear from the items of Table (6) that the environmental education domain means ranged between 3.03 (highest) which was for the item providing: "Develops the ethical values with the students in a way that helps in activating the positive relation between the human and environment", and 2.33 (lowest), which was for the item providing, "Develops a sense of the individual and collective responsibility in protecting the environment through the one-team work spirit and through participation in solving the environmental problems". On the other hand, the domain, as a whole, came with medium mean (2.64) and (0.83) standard deviation. The researcher ascribes this medium level to the ineffectiveness of the faculty members in strengthening the global citizenship values in the students' behaviors and their feeling of belonging to a wider community that transcends the national borders. The behaviors that highlight the "common dividers" among the humans, which are fed and nourished by interconnections between the local and global levels, on the one hand, and the national and international levels, on the other.

Results of the second question: Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) level in the study sample evaluations of the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University in reinforcing the values of the global citizenship according to the gender and faculty variables?

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations of the sample participants' responses about the role of the faculty members of the Hashemite University in strengthening the global citizenship values as per the (gender, college) variables were obtained Thereafter, the researcher applied the 2-Way ANOVA statistical test, as illustrated in Tables (7, 8).

Table (7): Means and Standard Deviations of the Sample Participants' Responses on the Role of the Sports Activities According to the Gender and College Variables.

Variable	Level	M	SD
Gender	Male	2.99	0.65
	Female	2.49	1.11
College	Education	2.75	1.25
	Arts	2.71	1.42
	Science	2.68	0.83

Table (7) indicates apparent differences among the means of the sample participants' responses on the role of the sports activities according to the gender and college variables. To obtain the statistical significance of these differences, the Two-Way ANOVA analysis was applied, as provided in table (8).

Table (8): Results of the Two-Way ANOVA Analysis on the Responses of the Sample Participants about the Hashemite University Faculty Members' Role in Strengthening the Global Citizenship Values as per the Gender and College Variables.

Source	Total Squares	Freedom Degrees	Squares Mean	F	Sign.
Gender	1.68	1	1.68	3.01	0.02
College	9.22	2	4.61	1.17	0.91
Error	223.52	846	0/26		
Total	2732.00	850			

Table (8) shows statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) level in the role of faculty members in strengthening the global citizenship values that are ascribed to the gender variable, in favor of the males. This may be due to the nature and norms of the community that highlight the prominence of the male's role, which cause the emergence of the male faculty members in supporting the global citizenship values and urging to fix them with the males, as well as their tendency in their lectures, more than the female faculty members. The results of this study are in line with the study of Abu Salamiah (2009), which showed statistically significant differences in the views of the students about the role of the faculties of education in the Palestinian universities in supporting the citizenship, which was also in favor of the males.

Meanwhile, the results did not show statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) level in the role of faculty members in strengthening the global citizenship values that are ascribed to the faculty variable, as F was (1.71), which a non-statistically significant value. This is attributed to that the mechanism of supporting the global citizenship is similar in all the colleges, which meet in one educational environment, one atmosphere, and one campus.

Recommendations

In the light of the study results, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1- Developing a plan for the continuous course of civics education and enriching it with more activities that support the values of the global citizenship.
- 2- Holding workshops and courses that enhance the values and concepts of the global civics education.
- 3- The Media should focus on preparing and implementing programs related to the national, political and social concepts, because educating the citizen is the responsibility of all the state systems.

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Author Information

Fawwaz Yasein Salman

Faculty of Educational Sciences and Faculty of Physical Education and Sport Sciences, the Hashemite University, Jordan

Ibrahim Mohammad Harafsheh

Faculty of Educational Sciences and Faculty of Physical Education and Sport Sciences, the Hashemite University, Jordan
